

DETAILED HISTORY OF KANG STATE.

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Annotation: We know that it was once again in the event of the ancient times the land of the ancient times, during the Kublish state. The origins of the word of the word, information about the history, residents and troops of these people in many sources, confirms that there is another great state in this round basis. In this article, valuable information has been provided with various views, geographical locations, centers of the winter, with a variety of sources and individual conclusions.

Keyword: Accyctional, Abulqasim Prandate, Authority, Akimov, Kandh and Huns.

In ancient times, the state of Kang, which existed in the middle basin of the Syrdarya, was one of the great states of its time (between the third century BC and the middle of the fifth century AD). It can be seen in some literature that the inhabitants of this country are also called by this name. Scientist K. Shaniyozov said that the Kang state bordered on Ferghana (Davan, Dayyuan) in the east, Usun (Uyshun) states in the northeast, and the lands in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya in the northwest. According to Chinese sources, the territory of the Kang state also included the Tashkent oasis, the lands in the Talas and Chu river valleys. In some historical periods, the present-day Samarkand, Shahrisabz, Urganch city, Kattakorgan and Bukhara were also seen, and its borders reached Amudarya. According to this source, the population consists of 120,000 families or 600,000 people. In some sources, this Kang state is also mentioned as "Kengaras". However, scientists say that this word means "Kang'ar-as", that is, the people of the Kang' state. There are assumptions that the name of the "Kenagas" among the Uzbek clans is related to the name of that tribe. The inhabitants of this country, who believed in the Blue God, were mainly made up of the Kangli, Kipchak, Kengaras and Bajnaq clans. Qarluq and Oguz tribes also lived in these areas. Turkish script was used.

Information about the state of Kang can be found in many Chinese chronicles. According to I. Marquardt, Kangar was a political name (name of the state) in its time and had no relation to its ethnonym. However, contrary to his opinion, he equates the word Qanguy mentioned in Chinese chronicles with the ethnonym Qandar (Kang'ar) mentioned in Ptolemy.

The word Qang' (Qang'a) is equated to the city of "Kankha" mentioned in the Avesta. According to Firdausi's "Shahnoma", Qandez was considered the central city of the kings of Tur. The Shak tribes were said to be species. It was imagined that the ancient lands of these Shakas were on the other side (north) of the Syrdarya. The middle course of the Syrdarya is mentioned as the Kangar river in Ibn Khordatbekh's reports of the beginning of the 8th century.

In Abulqasim Firdavsi's work "Shahnoma" the places in the middle stream of Syr Darya are called Kang'a river, and Kang'a region is located in the northern part of Isfajab (in O'tror region). If we take a closer look, the information about the area where the Kanga River is

located in this "Shahnoma" by Abulqasim Firdawsi turns out to be the same as the location of Kangu Tarban in the inscriptions of Urhun.

The Byzantine Emperor Constantine Bagryanorodny (905-959) in his historical work entitled "On the Administration of the Empire" mentions that there is a tribe called "Kangar" among the Bijanaks living in the deserts of South Russia. In his opinion, the meaning of the word "Kang'ar" is valor, bravery. We can say that the word "Kang'ar" means brave and valiant people. Of course, historical scholars must have reflected in their work the understanding of the Kangars about their names (the interpretation of the word "Kanghar" that exists among the people). S.E. said that it is difficult to say that the original meaning of the word "Kangar" was determined with the interpretation provided by Konstantin Bagryanorodny. It can be learned from the information provided by Malov.

We can find a lot of mutually confirming and sometimes contradictory opinions and historical facts about the origin of kangas and their location. These scientific assumptions of Marquardt, Al-Idrisi, Chuloshnikov are a clear example of this.

Another important information about the Kang' people can be obtained from the works of Al-Idrisi (XII). Al-Idrisi mentions in his works one of the tribes located near the Aral Sea, in the north and northeast of it, as Khangakishi, i.e. Kang people. The interpreter of this word is S.G. According to Klyashtorny, the Turks adopted the ethnonymic suffix "Arni" present in the Tokhalar language, and later gave the meaning of the word "Ar" as a person in their language. The Qang'ar-as (Kang'ar-ash) ethnic group, which existed in the early Middle Ages, kept its name even in the later periods of the Middle Ages. The meaning of this name must be the people of Kang, i.e. the people living on the banks of the river "Kang". The ethnonym Qan-he-li is found in Chinese chronicles of the 7th century AD. The Chinese transcription of this name reads as Kangharlik. This name given in Chinese sources is one of the earliest variants of the Kangli ethnos.

There are some legends among the people about the origin of the word Kangli. Rashid-ad-din (second half of the 13th century) connects the origin of the word Kangli with the legendary person Oguzkhan. According to legends, Oghuz Khan made a cart to transport the wealth he acquired during the wars with his clans. The chariot is called "Kang'li" in Turkish. That is why they (Oguz Khan and his dependents) were called Kangli. All Kangans are considered their descendants. Similar information is given in "Tawarikh-i Guzida-Nusratname" written at the end of the 15th century and the beginning of the 16th century. In the play, the spoils of the war between Oguz Khan and his father were carried on carts. "Kang'li" is called a cart in Turkish. Their descendants formed the Kangli tribe.

Other historians have different opinions. In particular, Abu-l Ghazi attributes the appearance of the word "Kangli" to the troops of Oghuz Khan. Even if Oguz Khan tried to take away all the spoils that he won after winning the war, most of them remained. A clever man from his army invents a cart. The reason why the cart is called kanga is that it makes a sound like "Kang-kang" when it moves. The person who made and invented the first chariot was called Kangli, and all the people of Kangli were considered to be descendants of this person.

If we pay attention to the above information, the word Kang' has been known since ancient times. The origin of the word "Kang'" is attributed to Rashid-ad-Din Oguzkhan, and Abul-Gazi to other people, that is, he was not from the Oguzkhan clan. The origin of the word "Kang" and the geographical location of the people with this name are always disputed. Historical sources

contain a lot of valuable information about the founding of the Kang state and the state as a whole.

The first political system established by the Kangars is called the "Kang State". In ancient Chinese sources, valuable information about the presence of a state in the Kangars dates back to the end of the 3rd century and the beginning of the 2nd century BC. Of course, it would be wrong to understand that the Kangar state was formed in that period. As a result of the study of the chronicles, information was found that the state of Kang was formed even earlier. Academician Y.G. According to Ghulamov, the state of Kang came into existence at the end of the 4th century and the beginning of the 3rd century BC.

There were many cities in the ancient Kang state and they performed various tasks. Due to the fact that the country consists of a union of settled regions and pastoral peoples, the capital of the Kang state was located in two places. One is for a village in a settled oasis, and the other is the basis of a large part of the state's land and country properties, and is settled in vast pastures to manage cattle farms. The winter residence is in the city of Qang'dez, which is located on the coast of Yosha (Syr Darya). In ancient Chinese sources, this city was called Bitian. Its ruins have been preserved to this day in the form of a hill. The monument is called Kanqatepa. This monument is located 70 km south of Tashkent on the banks of the dried-up old bed of the Ohangaron river, an old tributary of the Syrdarya. According to archaeologists, as early as the 3rd century BC, Kang'dez was a large city with five parts, consisting of an arch, three cities and a rabad, surrounded by a strong defensive wall. Its area is equal to 160 hectares. In terms of prestige, Qangdez is located among historical cities such as Samarkand, Nakhlab (Yerkurgan), Bukhara.

The army of the Kang state consisted of 80-90 thousand warriors. The customs of the inhabitants of this country were similar to those of the Hun tribes. Godlike relations were established between the ruler of the country of Kang and Tangrikuti of the Hun Khanate. For this reason, when the Chinese defeated the Huns and pushed them out of their place, the Khan Khan moved to the Kang state with his descendants. The nomadic population of the Kang state was engaged in animal husbandry, and the settled population living in cities and their surroundings engaged in agriculture, handicrafts, and trade.

In the second half of the 5th century AD, the state of Kang disintegrated, and Shosh (Shi in Chinese sources), Samarkand (Kan), Maymurg (Mi), Shahrisabz (Shi), Kattakorgan (Xe), Ustrushona (Sao) were located in its territory. two countries are formed. Over time, these territories were gradually incorporated into the Ephthalite state. Monuments from the period of the Kang state were found in the excavations of Jonboskala Koykirilan fortress, Kichik Kirqqiz, Kunarli fortress, White fortress and other fortresses in the Khorezm oasis.

In conclusion, the information about the Kang state is very important for the history of Uzbek statehood. In due time, the Kangs were able to create large and powerful states of the Turonda period in this land. The emergence of new branches of the economy caused this power to increase even more. The Kangs are the founders of the state, which ruled the history scene for around 800 years or even longer.

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